

DEVELOPMENT AND HISTORY OF PEDAGOGICAL THOUGHTS

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Annotation: In this thesis, the scientific thought in the field of pedagogy, the development of ideas and the process of its historical formation are discussed based on the discussion.

Key words: pedagogical activity, age groups, discussion, conscious approach, principle of activity, principle of education.

INTRODUCTION

In every social system, there are concepts such as education, spirituality and enlightenment, which ensure the spiritual growth of a person, and they require the study of changes in the field of pedagogy in connection with the development of society. In every social system, there are concepts such as education, spirituality and enlightenment, which ensure the spiritual growth of a person, and they require the study of changes in the field of pedagogy in connection with the development of society.

The history of pedagogy has been studying the development of the theory of education, school and pedagogy in different periods from ancient times to the present day based on the demand of the development of times. Every social system, its future is directly related to the prospects of humanity, people's living standards and the development of science and culture. The history of pedagogy has been studying the development of the theory of education, school and pedagogy in different periods from ancient times to the present day based on the demand of the development of times. Every social system, its future is directly related to the prospects of humanity, people's living standards and the development of science and culture.

The history of world pedagogy and the history of development, the historicity of world educational ideas, the primitive community system was replaced by a new social pharmaceutical slavery system in the later periods of historical development.

Indeed, during historical development, different countries and peoples have developed world culture through different approaches. For example: paper was invented in China, the decimal system of counting was discovered in India, and in Mesopotamia it was invented to divide the globe into degrees, and the day into hours, minutes and minutes. Indeed, during historical development,

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Plutarch, an ancient Greek historian and philosopher, spoke about education in Spartan schools and said: "When it came to reading and writing, children were taught the bare necessities, and the rest of the education had one goal: to obey without words, to be patient." "It was intended to teach the science of living and conquering" Another important task of Spartan education was to educate young people to be cruel and disdainful of slaves. For this purpose, young people took part in "Creptiyas", i.e., in the streets, in the exercise of catching slaves, and killed slaves who looked suspicious. When the young men reached the age of 18-20, they did military service in the youth group "Ephebs".

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In Sparta, special attention is paid to the education of girls. They were armed with military and physical training skills. Because when men went to war, they guarded the city and kept the slaves obedient, and even participated in the battles. In Athens, discipline, school system and education were completely different from Spartans.

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The ancestors of the current Uzbek people lived several thousand years ago, and they went a long and hard way to create a unique culture. The history of our ancestors up to the period from the use of weapons for livelihood to the development of more advanced tools, economic life and cultural development by the time of seed production is evidence of the rich ancient culture of our ancestors.

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In the first millennium BC, various tribes and peoples lived in such countries as Bactria, Khorezm, Sogdiyona, Margiyana, Parthia and Parkana.

The teachings of Abu Nasr Farabi allama about human perfection are of great importance in the field of education. After the famous Greek philosopher Aristotle, they call him the second teacher in the East "Teacher Sani". It is said that Abu Nasr Farabi knew more than 70 languages. In his works on education, Farabi reflects on the methods and methods of education, what needs to be paid attention to in education. His works such as "The City of Virtuous People", "About the Attainment of Happiness", "About the Meanings of the Mind" express the socio-educational views of scholars.

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